

Original article

Stage of fibrosis is not a predictive determinant of weight loss in patients undergoing bariatric surgery

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Abstract

Background: Obesity and nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) are an increasing health care burden worldwide. Weight loss is currently the best option to alleviate NAFLD and is efficiently achieved by bariatric surgery. Presence of NAFLD seems to be predictive for postoperative weight loss. To date, only few predictive factors for postbariatric weight loss (age, diabetes, psychiatric disorders) are established.

Objectives: Since liver fibrosis is the pathogenic driver for the progression of liver disease, we investigated its role in predicting postoperative weight loss. This study focuses on the correlation between fibrosis stage and weight loss.

Setting: University and university-affiliated cooperation, Germany.

Methods: We used a prospective, single-center cohort study including 164 patients who underwent bariatric surgery with simultaneous liver biopsies. Liver fibrosis was determined histologically according to Kleiner score and noninvasively by APRI and FIB-4 score. Percentage of total body weight loss was calculated at 1-year follow up visit.

Results: Thirty-two patients were found without fibrosis, whereas 91 patients showed mild fibrosis (F1), 37 significant fibrosis (F2), and only 4 patients presented advanced fibrosis (F3) at the time of bariatric surgery. Weight loss was similar across different degrees of fibrosis stage. Accordingly, linear regression analysis did not identify predictors of weight loss among fibrosis scores. In multivariable analysis, age and presence of diabetes showed the strongest predictive value.

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Conclusions: Baseline presence of fibrosis was not associated with postoperative weight loss, while age and diabetes were independent predictors of weight loss. Bariatric surgery should be applied independently of the fibrosis stage. (*Surg Obes Relat Dis* 2024; ■:1–8.) © 2024 American Society for Metabolic and Bariatric Surgery. Published by Elsevier Inc. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: Bariatric surgery; Weight loss; Liver fibrosis; Noninvasive test; NAFLD

Obesity is one of the major public health concerns, with an increasing prevalence worldwide and causing an immense health care burden [1]. Therefore, the world health organization announced obesity to be the pandemic of the 21st century.

Concomitantly, the prevalence of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and its more severe form of nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) has markedly increased in the last decades, currently affecting about 25% of the whole population [2]. NAFLD is presently the most common cause of chronic liver disease and significantly increases hospital admissions for cirrhosis, while it will shortly overtake alcoholic liver disease as the most frequent indication for liver transplantation at least in the United States [1,3].

For chronic liver disease, liver fibrosis is the main determinant of disease progression as it is responsible for liver-related complications [4]. Since currently no antifibrotic drugs are approved neither by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) nor the European Medicines Agency, prevention and treatment of the underlying liver disease is the best option to halt disease progression.

In this context, bariatric surgery is an effective therapy, since it leads to sustained weight loss and thereby is capable to resolve NASH [5,6]. Recently, a large retrospective study showed superiority of bariatric surgery compared to nonsurgical care as it significantly lowered the risk of major adverse liver outcomes and cardiovascular events [7].

Multiple factors have been described to negatively influence postoperative weight loss, such as low preoperative high density lipoprotein (HDL) and folic acid levels, psychiatric disorders, and presence of NASH [8–10]. It is acknowledged that bariatric surgery influences the course of fibrosis [11–13], but the role of liver fibrosis for postoperative weight loss still remains unknown. We investigated the association of liver fibrosis with weight loss in bariatric patients.

Methods

Study design

This prospective, monocentric, observational study was performed at the Department of Bariatric, Metabolic, and Plastic Surgery at the St. Franziskus-Hospital Cologne (Germany) between July 2018 and January 2021. The department is a tertiary care center performing around 400 primary and 100 bariatric revisional procedures per year.

The study was approved in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki by the Ethics Committees of the Aerztekammer Nordrhein (Project identification code 2017110) and the University of Bonn (Project identification code 194/17).

Patient consent statement

Signed informed consent was obtained from all patients prior to inclusion in written form.

Study population

During the study period, we performed a total of 1200 surgical procedures in our center, of which 962 were primary bariatric surgeries. In line with international and German guidelines for bariatric surgery, indication to surgery was established when conservative procedures were exhausted (reduction in initial weight of <15% for a BMI of 35–39.9 kg/m² and <20% for a BMI over 40 kg/m² has not been achieved. All patients took part in preoperative multimodal weight loss programs. The majority participated in our center-bound programs. Those with body mass index (BMI) between 35 and 50 kg/m² followed our 6-month concept with monthly nutritional counselling, behavioral therapy, theory concerning physical activity with obesity, and practical physical activity with a documented minimum of 2.5 hours per week. In BMI >50 kg/m², patients followed a shortened 3 - month program with the same modules. These preoperative programs under professional guidance were in accordance with national and international guidelines and recommendations concerning conservative treatment of obesity. In addition, all patients received preoperative psychological assessment to exclude contraindications like severe eating disorders, untreated addictions, and relevant psychological or psychiatric disorders.

All patients planned for either one Anastomosis/Mini-gastric bypass or Roux-en-Y gastric bypass were screened for inclusion during the study period. According to our study protocol we only enrolled patients with either primary Roux-en-Y gastric bypass or primary One anastomosis/Mini-gastric bypass in this study. The decision for one or the other of these two procedures was taken considering patients' BMI, fat distribution type, preoperative severity of gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), necessity of multiple psychotropic medications and of course patients' preferences. Patients with higher BMI (>50 kg/m²), abdominal fat distribution type, less GERD symptoms, absence of

larger hiatal hernia (>5 cm) and no need for multiple psychotropic medications were mainly addressed towards One Anastomosis Gastric Bypass. Exclusion criteria were as follows: age below 18 years old, alcohol consumption above 1 standard drink per day (=20 g ethanol/day), presence of hepatopathy of any other etiology than metabolic and clinical and/or histopathological evidence of liver cirrhosis, previous bariatric bypass surgery, surgical revisions and/or conversion-procedures. Of the 241 patients receiving primary bariatric bypass surgery as a treatment for morbid obesity in this study, 164 patients attended the 1-year follow-up visit. The patients were offered the opportunity to participate in voluntary clinical and nutritional follow-up assessments twice a year. The 3 years follow-up visit was attended by 38% of the study population. Reasons for nonparticipations were not recorded.

Standard laboratory findings and noninvasive tests at baseline

Standard laboratory findings (white blood cell count, hemoglobin, platelets, INR, electrolytes, creatinine, transaminases, gamma-glutamyl transferase, alkaline phosphatase, total bilirubin and albumin) were determined in order to obtain previously published and commonly used noninvasive scores for every patient. In detail, in this study we calculated the aspartate aminotransferase (AST) to Platelet Ratio Index (APRI) and the fibrosis-4 (FIB-4) score. Formulae and calculation algorithms as well as the utilized thresholds are provided in Table 1 [14,15].

Liver biopsy

Liver samples were taken as described previously [9]. A wedge liver biopsy of approximately 1 cm³ was removed immediately after trocar placement from Couinaud segment III. Liver biopsies were processed according to standard protocols in the Institute for Pathology (University Hospital of Cologne, Germany). Sections were stained with Gomori stain.

Histopathological evaluation

Fibrosis assessment was performed in a blinded fashion according to the “Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease Activity Score System” from the Nonalcoholic Steatohepatitis Clinical Research Network Study Group (NASH-CRN) [16] by 2 expert pathologists at the Department of Pathology in Cologne (Germany). Briefly, fibrosis was classified as follows: 0 - absence of fibrosis; 1a - mild pericellular fibrosis, only detectable in trichrome stain; 1b - moderate pericellular fibrosis, readily detectable on H&E stain; 1c - only portal fibrosis with no pericellular fibrosis; 2 portal fibrosis (any) and pericellular fibrosis (any); 3 bridging fibrosis. Grades 1a, 1b and 1c were summarized as grade 1 for statistical analysis.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis and plots were performed using SPSS Statistics (Version 26, IBM, Armonk, NY). Descriptive statistics were computed for all variables. Categorical variables were reported as absolute frequency (n) and percentage (%). Continuous variables were described by median and interquartile range (IQR). For categorical variables, Chi-square tests were used in univariate analyses. Nonparametric tests (Kruskal–Wallis H test) were used for comparison of quantitative variables between groups. Predictive power was calculated through linear regression, significance was calculated via analysis of variance (ANOVA). Multivariate analysis was performed in order to check for confounding variables. A P-value below .05 was considered significant for all analyses.

Results

164 patients were analyzed in this study. The patients were stratified based on their degree of fibrosis in the liver histology. Fig. 1 shows representative Gomori stains for each degree of fibrosis.

Table 1
Noninvasive tests for liver fibrosis

Name	Formula	Reference
AST-to-platelet ratio index (APRI)	$\frac{AST \left[\frac{U}{L} \right] / ULN \left[\frac{U}{L} \right]}{\text{platelet count} \left[\frac{10^9}{L} \right]} \times 100$	Wai et al. [14]
Fibrosis-4 (FIB-4)	$\frac{\text{Age [years]} \times AST \left[\frac{U}{L} \right]}{\text{platelet count} \left[\frac{10^9}{L} \right] \times \sqrt{ALT \left[\frac{U}{L} \right]}}$	Sterling et al. [15]

ALT = Alanine aminotransferase; AST = aspartate aminotransferase; ULN = upper limit of the normal.

Standard non-invasive liver fibrosis tests. The ULN is 35 U/l for women and 50 U/l for men. Presence of diabetes includes 0 (absence) or 1 (presence).

Fig. 1. Representative Gomori stain for each stage of fibrosis. F0: absence of liver fibrosis, F1: pericellular fibrosis or portal fibrosis without pericellular fibrosis, F2: presence of both pericellular and periportal fibrosis and F3: bridging fibrosis including fibrotic septa from one portal field to another. The scale bar is 200 μm . F = Fibrosis.

Study cohort

Table 2 shows the general characteristics of our cohort. According to the pathological scoring system, 32 patients (19.5%) did not show liver fibrosis, whereas 55.5% showed

F1-fibrosis, 22.6% showed F2-fibrosis and only 2.4% showed advanced liver fibrosis (F3). Median age ranged from 41 to 44 years. Median body mass index (BMI) ranged from 46.5 kg/m^2 in the F0-group to 53.8 kg/m^2 in the F3-group suggesting higher degrees of fibrosis in patients with higher body weight,

Table 2
Characteristics prior to enrollment, in patients without fibrosis (F0), mild fibrosis (F1), significant fibrosis (F2), and advanced fibrosis (F3)

Characteristic	F0 (n = 32)	F1 (n = 91)	F2 (n = 37)	F3 (n = 4)	P value
Data at baseline					
Age, yr, median (IQR)	44 (35–51)	41 (33–51)	44 (38–53)	44 (39–60)	.469
Female sex, n (%)	28 (87.5)	77 (84.6)	30 (81.1)	4(100)	.731
Body mass index, kg/m^2 , median (IQR)	46.5 (42.1–51.1)	49.7 (44.8–54.5)	49.4 (44.7–56.1)	53.8 (43.3–66.6)	.058
Obesity-related comorbidities, n (%)					
Arterial hypertension	17 (53.1)	55 (60.4)	28 (75.7)	3 (75.0)	.223
Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome	20 (62.5)	62 (68.1)	22 (59.5)	3 (75.0)	.764
Coronary heart disease	0 (.0)	1 (1.1)	0 (.0)	0 (.0)	.848
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	5 (15.6)	30 (33.0)	18 (48.6)	4 (100.0)	.001*
Musculoskeletal disorder	28 (87.5)	88 (96.7)	36 (97.3)	4 (100.0)	.061
Type of bariatric surgery, n (%)					
One Anastomosis/Mini-Gastric Bypass (OAGB-MGB)	24 (75.0)	81 (89.0)	33 (89.2)	4 (100.0)	.162
Duration of bariatric surgery, min, median (IQR)	75 (65.3–89.5)	75 (65–90)	80 (68.5–94)	84 (68.75–112)	.535
Duration of postoperative hospitalization, d, median (IQR)	3 (3–3)	3 (3–3)	3 (3–3)	4 (3–6.5)	.209

Clinical characteristics and baseline data prior to enrollment in patients without fibrosis (F0), mild fibrosis (F1), significant fibrosis (F2) and advanced fibrosis (F3). P-values were obtained using chi-square test or Kruskal-Wallis-Test. P-values <.05 were considered statistically significant (*).

Table 3

Laboratory findings and noninvasive scores for liver fibrosis prior to enrollment, in patients without fibrosis (F0), with mild fibrosis (F1), significant fibrosis (F2) and advanced fibrosis (F3)

Characteristic	F0 (n = 32)	F1 (n = 91)	F2 (n = 37)	F3 (n = 4)	P value
Biomarker scores prior to bariatric surgery,					
median (IQR)					
AST-Platelet Ratio Index (APRI)	.22 (.18–.25)	.24 (.19–.37)	.31 (.21–.45)	.47 (.30–.77)	.003*
FIB-4 Score	.63 (.54–1.01)	.70 (.48–.98)	.81 (.56–1.07)	1.08 (.96–1.29)	.071
Laboratory findings median (IQR)					
White-cell count, $\times 10^9/L$	7.5 (6.7–8.5)	7.6 (6.6–8.7)	7.7 (7.0–9.0)	7.9 (7.5–10.6)	.615
Hemoglobin, g/dL	13.4 (13.0–14.4)	13.9 (13.1–14.7)	14.0 (13.2–15.2)	14.1 (13.6–14.8)	.189
Platelet count, $\times 10^9/L$	279 (243–316)	281 (242–337)	299 (266–325)	262 (173–301)	.429
Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), U/L	24 (17–31)	32 (22–50)	40 (30–58)	52 (37–67)	.002*
Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), U/L	22 (19–25)	26 (21–35)	33 (27–46)	42 (34–47)	<.001*
Gamma-glutamyltransferase (gGT), U/L	23 (16–31)	27 (21–37)	30 (25–49)	44 (30–55)	.110
Alkaline phosphatase (AP), U/L	80.5 (68–96)	75 (62–90)	79 (68–86.5)	69.5 (66.5–80.5)	.452
Serum total bilirubin, mg/dL	.5 (.3–.6)	.5 (.4–.7)	.6 (.4–.8)	.6 (.5–.6)	.249
Serum albumin, g/dL	43.0 (40.1–44.2)	42.1 (40.5–43.5)	43.1 (41.5–44.4)	42.3 (37.1–43.0)	.434
International Normalized Ratio (INR)	1.01 (.97–1.05)	1.01 (.98–1.04)	1.01 (.99–1.04)	1.08 (1.03–1.11)	.216
Serum creatinine, mg/dL	.8 (.7–.9)	.8 (.8–.95)	.9 (.73–1.0)	1.0 (.75–1.0)	.036*

Laboratory findings and noninvasive scores for liver fibrosis prior to enrollment, in patients without liver fibrosis (F0), with mild fibrosis (F1), significant fibrosis (F2) and advanced fibrosis (F3). *P*-values were obtained using Kruskal–Wallis-Test. *P*-values <.05 were considered statistically significant (**P* <.05).

though not significant (*P* = .058). The presence of obesity-related comorbidities did not vary significantly in our groups except for the type 2 diabetes mellitus. Diabetes was present in 15.6% of patients without liver fibrosis, in 33.0% with F1-fibrosis, in 48.6% with F2-fibrosis and in all patients showing F3-fibrosis (*P* = .001). Median operation time was similar across fibrosis stages (*P* = .535).

Table 3 displays the noninvasive scores for liver fibrosis and preoperative laboratory findings. As expected, medians of APRI and FIB-4 score increased with higher degree of fibrosis. The increase was significant for APRI (*P* = .003) but showed only a trend for FIB-4 (*P* = .071). Interquartile range of laboratory values used for assessment of advanced liver damage (total bilirubin level, serum albumin, and International Normalized Ratio) were all within the reference range. However, we could detect elevated transaminases as indicators for Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NASH). As well as creatinine, alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and AST showed a significant increase with increasing fibrosis stage. In the study cohort, we could further calculate the noninvasive NASH detection score (NI-NASH-DS) [17] in a subset with available triglyceride levels (40 patients

(24%), in which we could confirm its predictive capacity with an AUC of .849 in our cohort.

Baseline histological fibrosis stage does not predict weight loss after bariatric surgery

Next, the association of the degree of fibrosis with postoperative weight loss was investigated. Table 4 shows preoperative and 1-year postoperative weight and body mass index (BMI) of our patients. During the 12-month follow up visit, total body weight was measured and percentage of total body weight loss (%TBWL) was calculated. Linear regression analysis showed no predictive power of histological fibrosis grade on 1-year postoperative body weight loss (R-square = .002, *P* = .583). Moreover, when checking for predictive power on postoperative BMI loss, the capacity was unchanged. Histological fibrosis grade could not predict postoperative weight loss.

Noninvasive fibrosis scores weakly predict weight loss after bariatric surgery

Hereafter, the predictive capacity of noninvasive tests for liver fibrosis was analyzed and its capacity to predict

Table 4

Percentage of total body weight and BMI loss, in patients without fibrosis (F0), with mild fibrosis (F1), significant fibrosis (F2), and advanced fibrosis (F3)

Characteristic	F0 (n = 32)	F1 (n = 91)	F2 (n = 37)	F3 (n = 4)	P value
%TBWL, %, median (IQR)	33.8 (27.3–40.1)	30.4 (26.8–39.0)	33.5 (26.5–39.8)	32.8 (25.6–41.8)	.878
BMI-Loss, kg/m ² , median (IQR)	15.4 (13.4–19.5)	15.3 (12.4–19.2)	16.2 (11.6–21.1)	17.4 (13.4–23.3)	.837

Percentage of total body weight loss and BMI loss, in patients without fibrosis (F0), with mild fibrosis (F1), significant fibrosis (F2) and advanced fibrosis (F3). *P*-values were obtained using Kruskal–Wallis-Test. *P*-values <.05 were considered statistically significant.

Table 5
Linear regression analysis of fibrosis and non-invasive fibrosis scores

Predictor	Outcome	R square	P-value
Histological grade of fibrosis	%TBWL after 1 yr	.002	.583
Histological grade of fibrosis	Loss of BMI after 1 yr	.002	.525
APRI	%TBWL after 1 yr	.032	.021*
APRI	Loss of BMI after 1 yr	.015	.123
FIB-4	%TBWL after 1 yr	.040	.011*
FIB-4	Loss of BMI after 1 yr	.026	.041*

Linear regression analysis of fibrosis and non-invasive fibrosis scores in order to evaluate the predictive capacity. *P*-values <.05 were considered statistically significant (*).

postoperative weight loss using linear regression was investigated. The APRI could significantly predict %TBWL after 1 year, but not the loss of BMI. However, R-square with .032 was relatively low. The FIB-4 score performed slightly better, being significant for both %TBWL and BMI loss. However, R-square presented poor model fit for %TBWL and BMI loss with .040 and .026, respectively (Table 5).

Overall, preoperative fibrosis grade did not determine postoperative weight loss. FIB-4 score weakly indicated the course of postoperative weight loss ($R = .20$).

Long-term course of postoperative weight loss remained stable at 3 years follow-up

Due to the potential for patients to experience weight regain in the long-term following bariatric surgery, we examined the extended weight trajectory of patients who attended voluntary follow-up visits (at 2 years: 69%, at 3 years: 38% of patients with available follow-up data). It

seemed that, following a fibrosis-independent similar weight loss at 12 months, F3-stage patients exhibited a more pronounced weight loss after 2 years, while weight trajectories had stabilized between 29% and 36% at 3-year follow-up visit (Fig. 2). At any timepoint, a significant difference emerged between the fibrosis groups (at 2 years: $P = .510$, at 3 years: $P = .609$).

Multivariable analysis revealed age and presence of diabetes mellitus as significant factors

Lastly, multivariable analysis of age, sex and presence of diabetes for the prediction of %TBWL at 1-year follow-up visit was performed. As expected, age and presence of diabetes had a significant negative impact on %TBWL at 1-year follow-up visit in the multivariable analysis (age: $P = .027$, diabetes: $P = .045$) (Table 6). Patients with diabetes had a lower probability of achieving a loss of BMI greater than 15 kg/m^2 (odds ratio = .564, 95% confidence interval

Long-term Course of Total Body Weight Loss (%TBWL) after bariatric surgery

Fig. 2. Long-term course of total body weight loss (%TBWL) after bariatric surgery across stages of fibrosis. %TBWL was plotted at baseline and 3, 6, 9, 12, 24 and 36 months postoperatively for F0, F1, F2 and F3 – patients. Data are plotted as medians. *P*-values were computed for the 12, 24 and 36 months follow-up data by Kruskal–Wallis test ($P = .405$, $P = .510$ and $P = .609$ for 12, 24 and 36 months follow-up respectively). No statistically significant differences were observed. F0 = no fibrosis; F1 = mild fibrosis; F2 = significant fibrosis; F3 = advanced fibrosis; mo = months; %TBWL = percentage of total body weight loss.

Table 6
Multivariable regression analysis of sex, age, and presence of diabetes on % TBWL

Dependent variable	Independent variable	P-value
%TBWL after 1 yr	Age	.046*
%TBWL after 1 yr	Sex	.620
%TBWL after 1 yr	Presence of diabetes	.041*

Multivariable regression analysis of sex, age and presence of diabetes on percentage of total body weight loss (%TBWL). P-values below .05 were considered statistically significant (*).

.295–1.087). Stage of fibrosis and sex were not predictive factors for postoperative weight loss.

Discussion

This observational study in patients with morbid obesity who underwent gastric bypass procedures aimed to evaluate the association of preoperative liver fibrosis stage with postoperative weight loss. Our study provides first evidence that preoperative degree of liver fibrosis was not associated with weight loss.

In 2023, a multisociety consensus statement on new nomenclature for fatty liver disease was published [18]. Since the study was recruited and analyzed before the publication of the consensus, we have retained the old nomenclature in this manuscript. However, since alcohol intake was an exclusion criterion and other causes of hepatopathy were excluded, all individuals would be classified with metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) in our study.

While recent research has developed noninvasive tools for NASH prediction [17], which we confirmed in a subset our cohort with available parameters, identification of liver fibrosis prior to bariatric surgery is challenging. Serum-based noninvasive scores are not accurate in individuals with obesity and need to be adjusted [19]. FibroTest®, a commercial serum-based noninvasive test for liver fibrosis, which is well validated using liver biopsy, is considered however to be inaccurate in individuals with morbid obesity [4,20]. Vibration-controlled transient elastography, which is currently the most accurate noninvasive method to measure liver stiffness showed low correlation with subjects with obesity in preoperative analyses [21]. Furthermore, it is hampered by the presence of hepatic inflammation, which is frequently present in patients with NASH, who comprises the largest cohort in fibrotic subjects undergoing bariatric surgery [22]. Liver biopsy still remains as the gold standard for the diagnosis of liver fibrosis, which was performed in our study.

Although gastric bypass surgery provides sustained weight loss in patients, there is a notable interindividual variability in terms of weight loss achievement [23]. Moreover, in the long term, patients after Roux-en-Y gastric bypass regularly regain weight [24]. Therefore, identifying

predictors of weight loss is crucial to better advise patients and to plan the clinical management. Despite already established factors for postoperative weight loss, we could previously show that baseline presence of NASH is negatively influencing weight loss, which was recently confirmed by another study investigating the 2-year postoperative course [9,25]. Well in line with this study, age and presence of diabetes are confounders in the prediction of postoperative weight loss according to multivariate analysis. Both factors had already been established as predictors of weight loss in previous studies [26,27].

While studies on the effect of preoperative liver fibrosis are scarce, changes in liver fibrosis after achieving weight loss were extensively studied. Moderate weight loss (5% TBWL) was shown to be not effective on liver fibrosis regression [28]. However, greater weight loss, usually achieved by bariatric procedures was demonstrated to promote fibrosis regression in both liver biopsy and in noninvasive tests [5,11,29,30]. Even in patients with early-stage compensated liver cirrhosis (Child-Pugh A), bariatric surgery seems to be safe, according to a small study including 22 patients with liver cirrhosis and a median liver stiffness of 15.4 kPa [31]. Our study adds into this concept by demonstrating that stage of fibrosis is not related to weight loss and is thereby promoting effectivity of bariatric surgery. However, in a large multicenter analysis, baseline variables were all considered to have limited predictive value for weight loss outcome [32]. In our study, though significant, FIB-4 had an R-square of .040, which displays very limited predictive value. Our study has several limitations. Patients with cirrhosis, with the severest fibrosis stage were not included in the study and could provide further additional information. The number of patients with advanced fibrosis (F3) was very low (n = 4) which renders statistical analysis difficult. Furthermore, 77 out of 241 patients did not attend the 1-year follow up visit.

Conclusion

Liver fibrosis most likely does not clearly indicate the quantity of weight loss after bariatric surgery, which was demonstrated by this study. More research is urgently needed to better advise patients and better select candidates for bariatric procedures. This study advocates for the use of bariatric surgery irrespective of stage of fibrosis.

Disclosure

The authors have no commercial associations that might be a conflict of interest in relation to this article.

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